

MIGRATION PATTERNS AND URBANISATION IN GWAGWALADA METROPOLIS, 2007–2020

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Abstract: *This study investigates migration patterns and urbanisation in Gwagwalada Metropolis, Abuja, between 2007 and 2020. It examines how urban drift shaped the town's demographic growth, settlement patterns, and socio-economic realities. The study adopted historical methodology; hence, it employed the use both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained through interviews with residents, community leaders, and stakeholders, while secondary data were drawn from census estimates, academic works, and government reports. Findings revealed that Gwagwalada's population has increased exponentially during the period of study which was influenced by both urban-to-urban migration from central Abuja and rural-to-urban migration from different parts of Nigeria. Push factors such as high living costs and demolition exercises in the central area of Abuja, alongside pull factors including affordable housing, the presence of the University of Abuja, and the Teaching Hospital, accounted for this drift. Consequently, this influx led to the expansion of informal settlements, overstretched infrastructure, and rising insecurity. The paper concludes that urbanisation in satellite towns creates opportunities and vulnerabilities, reflecting broader urban trends in Nigeria.*

Introduction

Urbanisation is a defining feature of developing African societies, often reshaping the demographic and socio-economic landscapes of

towns and cities. In Nigeria, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, has witnessed rapid expansion since the early 1990s, particularly following the restructuring and demolition of

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informal settlements in its central districts. These activities displaced thousands of residents, many of whom moved into satellite towns such as Lugbe, Nyanya, Kubwa, Kuje, and most notably, Gwagwalada.¹

Between 2007 and 2020, Gwagwalada experienced dramatic population growth, transforming from a semi-rural settlement into one of the fastest-growing satellite towns in Abuja. Census and population estimates suggest that Gwagwalada's population more than doubled within this period, stressing existing infrastructure and contributing to new socio-economic challenges.² Migration patterns into the town reflected both urban-to-urban and rural-to-urban movements, shaped by push factors such as congestion and high costs of living in central Abuja, and pull factors including affordable housing, government institutions, and

its strategic location along the Abuja–Lokoja expressway.

Urbanisation refers to the growth or expansion of towns and cities as people migrate from rural areas in search of better opportunities. Scholars describe it as both a demographic process and an economic transformation. Nels Anderson sees urbanisation as the concentration of people in cities, driven by industrial and population growth.³ Also, Bradshaw explains it as the shift from traditional agrarian communities to more modern, economically integrated urban societies.⁴ Hussain and Imityaz further explain that urbanisation involves not only population increase in urban areas but also the gradual development of urban characteristics such as improved infrastructure, administrative functions, and social services.⁵ In Nigeria, urban centres are often defined by their administrative

¹ Fanan, Ujo, Isa Kwabe, and Olarewaju Ifatimehin. "Understanding Urban Sprawl in the Federal Capital City, Abuja: Towards Sustainable Urbanisation in Nigeria." *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 3, no. 5, 2010, 6.

² Macrotrends. "Gwagwalada, Nigeria Metro Area Population 1950-2025." Macrotrends, 2025, <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/cities/206392/gwagwalada/population>. Accessed May 17 2025.

³ Nels Anderson. "Urbanism and Urbanization." *American Journal of Sociology*, 65, no. 1, 1959, 68.

⁴ York, Bradshaw. "Urbanisation and Underdevelopment: A Global Study of Modernization, Urban Bias, and Economic Dependency." *American Sociological Review*, 52, 1987, 224-239.

⁵ Manzoor, Hussain and Imityaz Iram. "Urbanisation Concepts, Dimensions and Factors." *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 9, no. 1, 2018

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roles and population density, meaning that even towns without major industries, such as Gwagwalada, acquire urban status because of their connection to Abuja and the expansion of services and housing around the Federal Capital Territory.

Satellite towns on the other hand are settlements established on the outskirts of a major city to support its growth by providing residential, administrative and commercial functions.⁶ In the case of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), towns such as Gwagwalada, Kuje, Bwari, and Kubwa were designated in the Abuja Master Plan to absorb population overflow, decentralize services and reduce pressure on the city centre.

Gwagwalada has a historical background dating back to the precolonial era. It was originally founded by the Bassa-speaking people led by Gbaga Daruwana, who settled in the area they called “Gbagala,” a name that evolved into “Gwagwalada” over time.⁷ Although the settlement remained small and administratively insignificant during the colonial period, its transformation began after the creation of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) in 1976. Gwagwalada became one of the six Area Councils of the FCT and was designated in the Abuja Master Plan as a major satellite town intended to

absorb population overflow from the city centre. Its administrative status, strategic location along the Abuja–Lokoja expressway, and proximity to key institutions such as the University of Abuja later contributed to its rapid urban growth.

Despite this rapid transformation, limited scholarly attention has been given to how migration patterns have shaped Gwagwalada’s urban growth within this period. Much of the existing urban research in the Federal Capital Territory focuses on central Abuja, leaving satellite towns like Gwagwalada understudied. As a result, there is inadequate documentation of the specific demographic movements, settlement patterns, and socio-economic changes influencing the town’s development.

This study examines the migration trends that defined Gwagwalada’s growth and development during the period under review, highlighting the factors that encouraged urban drift and the implications of this expansion. By analysing oral testimonies alongside secondary data, the paper provides insight into how Gwagwalada evolved into a dynamic urban centre and the socio-economic realities that accompanied this transformation. In doing so, the work contributes to broader discussion on the consequences of rapid urbanisation in

⁶ Evans, Dave, and O. W. Evans. *The Complete Real Estate Encyclopedia*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2007.

⁷ Abiye E. Ichaba. "The Peopling of Abuja Area of Nigeria in the 19th and 20th Centuries." *Research Guru: Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Subjects*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2017, 13

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developing societies, where urban expansion is often disconnected from industrialisation and formal employment opportunities.

Urban Drift towards Gwagwalada Metropolis

Historical Patterns of Migration

The period between 2007 and 2020 witnessed an urban-to-urban migration pattern especially at the early stage while the usual rural-to-urban migration was experienced in the later years in the study area. According to the Evert Lee in his Push-Pull Theory, urban-to-urban migration is the relocation of people from one urban town to another urban town.⁸ Lee explains that these patterns occur due to a number of factors such as congestion, high cost of living and pollution, which constitute the push factors while better career opportunities and improved living conditions constitute the pull factors.⁹

In the case of Gwagwalada, the pull factors were mostly not existent in Gwagwalada because, as of the period 2007 to 2020, Gwagwalada had a relatively low cost of living, did not offer better career opportunities than the main cities in Abuja such as Asokoro, Garki, Maitama, Wuse

and so on, and did not provide better living conditions. Therefore, migration from those main cities to Gwagwalada at the time was primarily for conditional shelter due to the reconstruction of Abuja Municipal towns and the eventual rise in the cost of living in these main city centre which had pushed people towards Gwagwalada.

In an interview with Mr. Igwe Solomon, he pointed out that for him and the majority of his friends at the time, these migrations were initially intended to be temporary, confirming that houses in Gwagwalada were affordable, and since many displaced people like himself who resided in Wuse II still had their businesses and jobs in Abuja, they had no choice but to remain within the FCT until a better solution was found.¹⁰ According to him, some of his friends had eventually relocated out of Gwagwalada to other states and some were eventually able to afford living in other satellite towns within the FCT such as Nyanya, Kubwa and Lugbe. However, he pointed out that some became established businessmen like himself there in Gwagwalada.¹¹

⁸ Lee, Everett S. "A Theory of Migration." *Demography*, vol. 3, no. 1, Population Association of America, 1966, 47-57.

⁹ Lee, Everett S. "A Theory of Migration." *Demography*, vol. 3, no. 1, Population Association of America, 1966, 47-57.

¹⁰ Interview with Igwe, Solomon. c55, Trader, Park Road, 18 Dec. 2024.

¹¹ Interview with Igwe, Solomon. c55, Trader, Park Road, 18 Dec. 2024.

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The study revealed that aside from the Hausa population, a majority of Gwagwalada's residents came from nearby states such as Kogi, Niger, and Benue. This does not imply that people from other states were not present in large numbers as well, but that rural-to-urban migration towards Gwagwalada was dominated by Hausas and people from neighbouring States. Meanwhile, migrants from distant states mainly relocated for job opportunities or business, with the Igbo population playing a major role in entrepreneurship. Some others like Mrs. Blessing Etim,¹² Mrs. Agatha Adam,¹³ and Dr. Afolabi Joseph¹⁴ noted that the nature of their job or spouse's job were the reasons for their relocation to Gwagwalada.

Several other informants confirmed this trend. For example, Mallam Khalifa, a political figure originally from Kano State, shared that in 2008 he moved from Maitama to Gwagwalada with his

father, who was a "Bureau de Change" operator.¹⁵ Similarly, Ojima, a lifelong resident of Gwagwalada, explained that her late father, who was a police officer, was transferred to the area and chose to settle there after retirement.¹⁶ Some other respondents such as Mr. Abdulrahman¹⁷ and Ene Mike¹⁸ gave career pursuit and job hunting as their reasons for migration towards Gwagwalada.

The majority of the Hausa population were, however, largely in pursuit of a better earning condition and most claim not to be permanent residents of Gwagwalada. According to information obtained from Mallam Bashir, their stay in Gwagwalada was purely business driven and therefore their families were not with them.¹⁹ He explained that this was the situation with him and most of his colleagues that had moved to Gwagwalada nearly seventeen years ago. They had only come for business and return

¹² Interview with Blessing Etim. 49, Stylist, Phase III, 16 Dec. 2024.

¹³ Interview with Mrs. Agatha Adam. 39, Nurse, Dagiri, 18 Dec. 2024.

¹⁴ Interview with Dr. Afolabi Joseph. 44, Medical Doctor, Jerimiah Hussein, 22 Dec. 2024.

¹⁵ Interview with Khalifa, Al-adam. c35, Political Elite and Realtor, Town Hall Axis, 16 Dec. 2024.

¹⁶ Interview with Ojima Gabriel. c31, Fashion Designer, Dagiri, 18 Dec. 2024.

¹⁷ Interview with Abdulrahman, Shakur. c32, Fashion Designer, FRCN Road, 22 Dec. 2024.

¹⁸ Interview with Mike, Ene. c32, Realtor, Angwan Dodo, 15 Dec. 2024.

¹⁹ Interview with Mallam, Bashir. 43, Trader, Kasuwan Dare Axis, 22 Dec. 2024.

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to their families on occasion and as a result, they had not considered renting a permanent residence in Gwagwalada.²⁰

Historically, therefore, the patterns of migration towards Gwagwalada had been a mix of both Rural to Urban and Urban to Urban. Reflecting Lee's theory of urbanisation, one can say that the pull factors attracted migrants towards the town while the push factors made Gwagwalada a viable option for people seeking to stay within the capital at a low cost or find it difficult to stay in the main towns of Abuja such as Maitama, Asokoro, Garki and Wuse, due to the cost or their congestion. Regardless of which of these factors, Gwagwalada between 2007 and 2020 had become one of the hottest satellite towns in Abuja with the influx of migrants.

Nature and Extent of Urban Drift in Gwagwalada, 2007–2020

Gwagwalada's population increased rapidly during the period from 2007 to 2020, reflecting the town's role as a major satellite settlement for Abuja and a primary destination for rural-urban migrants. According to the 2006 National Population Census head count, Gwagwalada's population was officially recorded at 158,618.²¹ The 2006 head count marked the last general census exercise in Nigeria as of 2020. However, Population estimates from Macrotrends population statistics estimated Gwagwalada's population at 133,000 by 2007 and 410,000 by 2020.²² These estimates represent a 208% increase over a 13-year period as shown in figure 4.1 below.

²⁰ Interview with Mallam, Bashir. 43, Trader, Kasuwan Dare Axis, 22 Dec. 2024.

²¹ Federal Republic of Nigeria. Official Gazette: Legal Notice on Publication of 2006 Census Final Results. Vol. 96, No. 2, 2 Feb. 2009, B1–B42.

²² Macrotrends. "Gwagwalada, Nigeria Metro Area Population 1950-2025." Macrotrends, 2025, <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/cities/206392/gwagwalada/population>. Accessed May 17 2025.

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Figure 4.1: Population Growth in Gwagwalada, 2007–2020

Source: Gwagwalada, Nigeria Metro Area Population 1950-2025. (Macrotrends, 2025)

Land use and land cover studies in the area confirm that Gwagwalada's physical footprint has expanded in tandem with its population. According to Belel, Zaheeda, Zaynab and Mahmood, the built-up area in Gwagwalada increased from 1,889.9 hectares in 2010 to 2,494.9 hectares in 2022, reflecting a percentage increase of 36.0% in twelve years.²³ While 2022 is slightly outside the scope of the current study, this data demonstrates the expansion of the area over a period of 10 years within the present study.

This rapid population and spatial growth resulted in the expansion of neighbourhoods within Gwagwalada town such as Dagiri,

Kutunku, Angwan Dodo, and Kasuwan Dare. These areas, which were previously inhabited mainly by indigenous Gwagwalada people and were sparsely populated by other groups or largely undeveloped as of 2007, but have become densely populated, with many new residential and commercial structures. The expansion has largely occurred in an unplanned manner, contributing to the proliferation of informal settlements.

Despite this growth, infrastructure development has not kept pace. Studies highlight persistent challenges in road networks, water supply, waste management, and housing quality, particularly in the rapidly expanding and poorly regulated neighbourhoods. The data demonstrate that Gwagwalada has experienced

²³ Belel, A. Waheeda, Belel A. Zaheeda, Belel A. Zaynab, and Mahmoud A. Hijab. "Implications of Urbanisation on Housing Condition in Gwagwalada

Town, Abuja, Nigeria." *Journal of Technology Management and Business*, 6, no. 2, 2019, 23-29.

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rapid and measurable urban drift since 2007, with the population nearly tripling and the built-up area estimated to have expanded by over 600 hectares in just over a decade. This unprecedented growth has transformed the town's demographic and spatial profile, creating new challenges for urban planning, infrastructure development and security.

Demographic Composition of People in Gwagwalada

It is important to note that the original inhabitants of Gwagwalada did not dominate the developed parts of the Area Council, referred to as Gwagwalada Metropolis, consisting of Phase I, Phase II, Phase III, FCDA Quarters, Angwan Dodo, Dagiri, Secretariat, New Kutunku, Kasuwan Dare, Abattoir Axis, and Dukpa. Instead, they were mainly found in surrounding villages such as Kilankwa, Passo, Bwako, Kwaita, Kaida, Paiko and Dobi. Therefore, Gwagwalada metropolis itself is primarily inhabited by settlers who relocated there over time. This was owing to the presence of government-owned institutions such as the University of Abuja (Mini Campus) and the Gwagwalada Specialist Hospital (Now University of Abuja Teaching Hospital - UATH), which attracted people to the town. In an

interview, Mr. Samuel Hashim explains that nearly half the population in areas like Phase I and Phase II consisted of students and university staff, stating that between 2010 and 2017, nearly all the houses in these areas had at least two student occupants.²⁴ However, due to the increased focus and use of the university's permanent site which is more on the out sketch of Gwagwalada, these student congestion had reduced over time.

It is safe to say that Gwagwalada's population growth and development were in response to the growing population created by the establishment of these government institutions. Gwagwalada town also experienced economic growth and infrastructure development because of these diverse populations. As of 2020, Gwagwalada town could boast of average water supply, interconnected roads, and electricity, even though respondents pointed out that the electricity supply had deteriorated in 2020 compared to a decade before it. Furthermore, many of the inner villages in Gwagwalada Area Council such as Kilankwa, Passo, Bwako, Kwaita, Kaida, Paiko and Dobi as of 2020 were yet to witness the level of development seen in Gwagwalada metropolis. In terms of population,

²⁴ Interview with Hashim, Samuel Personal interview. 30, Civil Servant, Phase II,16 Dec. 2024.

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these villages were also not comparable to Gwagwalada metropolis.

Factors Driving Urban Drift Towards Gwagwalada

Urban drift is influenced by various factors that either push individuals away from rural areas to urban centres or pull them toward urban centres. The “Push-Pull theory” by Everett Lee explains that migration is influenced by “push” factors, i.e., rural poverty, unemployment and “pull” factors, i.e. urban job opportunities and higher wages.²⁵ This theory posits that urban centres attract migrants because they offer better employment prospects, education, healthcare, and infrastructure. This is applicable to many Nigerian cities including Gwagwalada where this research’s findings shows that population growth in Gwagwalada between 2007 and 2020 can best be explained by factors such as:

Economic Opportunities: The pursuit of better employment prospects is a primary driver of migration to urban areas. Oded and David, explain that, migration is often a family or household decision, rather than an individual choice.²⁶ They argue that households send

members to cities for better income opportunities while urban earnings may be sent back as remittances to support the family in rural areas. In Gwagwalada for instance, several interviewees who were mainly migrants from nearby states explained that they had migrated in search of employment. In an interview with Mr. Abdulrahman, who is currently a tailor along FRCN Road, explained that his uncle had brought him to Gwagwalada to learn a trade as furthering education was difficult due to finances, after which he himself had paid forward the favour by bringing other young individuals who he had trained and had been working for him.²⁷

Another angle in which this can be viewed is Gwagwalada's proximity to the Abuja Municipal, which provided Gwagwalada residents access to jobs across various sectors, including commerce, education, and healthcare in the major towns of Abuja such as Wuse, Asokoro and the Central Area. A survey at the El Rufai Park and the SDP Park in Gwagwalada suggested that there were lots of people who worked in these cities under Abuja Municipal but resided in Gwagwalada town. This was not

²⁵ Lee, Everett S. “A Theory of Migration.” *Demography*, vol. 3, no.1, Population Association of America, 1966, 47-57.

²⁶ Stark, Oded, and David E. Bloom. "The New Economics of Labor Migration."

American Economic Review 75, no. 2, 1985, 173-178.

²⁷ Interview with Abdulrahman, Shakur. c32, Fashion Designer, FRCN Road, 22 Dec. 2024.

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limited to just traders or workers of former Abuja Municipal residents who relocated to Gwagwalada. The population of workers that resides in Gwagwalada and worked in those Municipal cities was large, with several interviewees confirming this trend to be more than a decade old.

Judging from inquiries of the park activities at the El-Rufai and SDP parks, buses began to load for Abuja Municipal cities as early as 6:30am, casual discussions with passengers showed that most of the workers cut across several industries such as government ministries, law firms, financial institutions, healthcare centres, and education sector among others. The morning period was not the only period reported for this sort of movement, during the early afternoons, people also moved in numbers to resume their shifts at their offices in town, though this number was not comparable to that of the morning hours. However, queues were noticeable. The researcher was able to understand that the average time of return from town by the workers began around 5:30pm until as late as 10:00pm.

One must take note that a pull factor according to Lee refers to the availability of industries, economic growth, average standard of living and the case of Gwagwalada does not apply directly to this theory. Gwagwalada in 2007 which begins the period of this research had no main industries worthy enough to amass the level of population it had, Government

institutions available in the area also had controlled level of employment, though it can be argued that these institutions such as the University of Abuja and its Specialist Hospital and the migration of people to work there had created opportunities for traders to drift in and satisfy the demands of the working class population as well as those of the students.

Therefore, Lee's theory is only plausible in Gwagwalada if one takes into consideration the mini market opposite the specialist hospital. No other government institution in Gwagwalada had created that much economic opportunities. However, another Institution that had amassed an economic minded population was the University of Abuja which had only its mini campus at the heart of the town, but the trade hub around the school was not exactly as promising as that of the teaching hospital as mainly school utilities and business centres existed there.

It is safe to say, judging from the above discussions, that the main economic pull factor that seduced people to migrate to Gwagwalada was not particularly in Gwagwalada but rather in Abuja Municipal towns such as Garki, Wuse, Asokoro and Central Area among others. It can be said that this trend created a sub-pull factor for business owners to utilize the population growth as an opportunity to thrive in Gwagwalada. However, Gwagwalada even as of 2020 was not the major business hub of Abuja nor was it a strategic point for business

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activities. Its economic prospects were mainly dependent of the residents of the area or passersby.

Infrastructure Development: The Modernisation Theory by Rostow suggested that economic and infrastructural development (e.g., roads, electricity, telecommunications) leads to urbanisation by attracting industries, services, and better living conditions.²⁸ According to this theory, Gwagwalada is expected to have had infrastructure development, since it seemed to have attracted population. However, Gwagwalada as of the year 2007 did not the infrastructural capacity to have attract the level population it did. Therefore, this study finds that population growth in Gwagwalada based on infrastructure can be linked to two factors. First is the establishment of the University of Abuja which played a very keen role in opening Gwagwalada to subsequent infrastructure development and secondly, its proximity to the Municipal cities of Abuja as discussed previously.

Michael Lipton's Urban Bias Theory also argues that Governments tend to invest heavily in

urban infrastructure, leading to rural underdevelopment and increasing urban drift.²⁹ This theory argues that infrastructure investments in cities create economic and social disparities, encouraging rural-to-urban migration. The theory also suggests that the intended city will most likely be endowed with good roads, health care centres, quality education etc. for the urban space to grow rapidly. This was close to the situation of Gwagwalada. However, it must be noted that in all factors listed above, education was one of the major threads of the region with the presence of the University of Abuja.

Regardless of the above theory, Gwagwalada is a town that had grown as a result of its location and not its endowments. Michael and Sunday posit that, Gwagwalada had grown significantly due to its strategic location along the Abuja-Lokoja expressway. They explained that, the town benefited and continues to benefit from infrastructural spillover from Abuja Municipal, attracting migrants looking for better opportunities.³⁰

²⁸ Rostow, W. W. *The Stages of Economic Growth: A Non-Communist Manifesto*. Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1960.

²⁹ Michael, Lipton. *Why Poor People Stay Poor: Urban Bias in World Development*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1977.

³⁰ Igbolo, Igbolo, Magdalene Agbor, and Sunday Simeon. "Labour Migration in the Federal Capital Territory: Examining Its Impact on the Socio-Economic Development of Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja." *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 22, no. 2, 2017, 4.

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These spillovers as explained by Michael and Sunday have attracted certain developments to Gwagwalada which earned her the title of the fastest developing satellite towns in Abuja. The educational hub due to the presence of the University of Abuja made Gwagwalada a knowledge centre. Students, academicians, and entrepreneurs migrated to the town, which boosted population growth and economic activities. Most of the academicians had also settled in Gwagwalada, building their own personal residences, same goes for the teaching hospital staff and many big traders in Gwagwalada during the study period.

Urban Amenities: Another factor that contributed to the influx of people to Gwagwalada was the easy access to urban amenities. The availability of specific amenities such as the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital (UATH), centralised water supply from LUD Water Works, educational facilities including the University of Abuja, planned residential areas (Phases 1, 2, and 3), and paved roads enhanced Gwagwalada's appeal as a desirable place to live. This is reflective in the Urban Bias theory which argues that rural areas are being neglected when it comes to these primary amenities and this neglect has long

been a reason for people migration out of rural areas in Nigerian societies.

Everett Lee's Push-Pull theory argues that the decision to migrate is influenced by a combination of positive and negative factors at both the origin and destination, including economic opportunities, infrastructure, and social amenities.³¹ In the same light, the modern economic theory argues that cities grow not just because of jobs but because people prefer locations with better urban amenities.³² Edward Glaeser, one of the proponents of this theory explained that urban migration is increasingly driven by the availability of amenities such as quality housing, public transportation, cultural institutions, and recreational opportunities.

In respect to the above, Gwagwalada provided at least a considerable access to these amenities and had grown to be a major city link between the Northern States and the Eastern, Western and Southern States. The expansion of the Lokoja Abuja Road made Gwagwalada increasingly attractive to traders and businesses. The parks and garages such as the SDP Park that mobilised people from Gwagwalada to Abuja Municipal, The Kano Zaria Park that mobilised people from Gwagwalada to the far North and the WAZOBIA

³¹ Lee, Everett S. "A Theory of Migration." *Demography*, vol. 3, no. 1, Population Association of America, 1966, 47-57.

³² Edward, L. Glaeser, Jed Kolko, and Albert Saiz, "Consumer City," *Journal of Economic Geography* 1, no. 1, 2001, 27–50.

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Park mobilised people from Gwagwalada to the Eastern, Western and Southern states. These parks were and still are along the Lokoja Abuja Road, these parks hosted and still hosts many petty traders who had set up kiosks and stores, which made the place busy at almost all times.

Access to education cannot also be overlooked, aside the importance of the University of Abuja which has already been discussed above, there were also secondary schools in their numbers in Gwagwalada. Gwagwalada had always been regarded as the educational hub of Abuja,³³ housing over ten Government-owned secondary schools such as GSS Gwagwalada, GDSS Gwagwalada, Hajj Camp Senior Secondary School, and School for the Gifted, among others. There is also the FCT School of nursing and several other privately owned educational institutions. All these, complemented with basic amenities of which Gwagwalada boasted of, such as availability of water, and health care services were contributing factors to the pull of people towards the area.

Urban Planning Initiatives in Gwagwalada Metropolis

Between 2007 and 2020, Gwagwalada Metropolis experienced significant urbanisation, which necessitated some

government interventions to manage its growth. Direct efforts by the government were made to elevate the available amenities to help balance Gwagwalada as an urban centre. The Federal Capital Development Authority (FCDA) implemented several plans and policies aimed at guiding the town's development during this period. Urban Planning initiatives during the period include:

Land Use Management: In 2007, to mitigate land-use conflicts arising from rapid urban expansion, the government emphasised the enforcement of zoning regulations. The approach aimed to delineate areas designated for residential, commercial, industrial, and recreational purposes, aimed at reducing conflicts and promoting organised development. Ekpeterere explained that:

In 2007, the FCDA revised the Gwagwalada Master Plan to address the rapid urbanisation and its associated challenges. This revision aimed to improve land use management, infrastructure development, and service delivery within the metropolis. The plan emphasized the need for proper zoning to separate residential, commercial, and industrial areas, thereby reducing land-use conflicts.³⁴

³³ University of Abuja, "Our Location," University of Abuja, <https://www.uniabuja.edu.ng/our-location>. Accessed 8 Jan. 2025.

³⁴ Ekpeterere, O. Kenneth. "Assessment of Land Use Conflict in Gwagwalada Town, FCT-Abuja." International Journal of

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These efforts could be said to have been successful to a reasonable extent. Research observations of the area showed that between 2007 and early 2015, the building layout of Gwagwalada town was defined and respected to an extent, commercial areas were purely commercial with schools, plazas and hotels taking the forefront while fuel and gas stations were situated on highways. However, most commercial structures such as schools, workshops, motels and eateries located within residential areas were found to have been developed in the later part of the decade leading up to 2020.

Research observations, corroborated by casual discussions with residents suggest that residential areas had increasingly become business areas, houses were converted to schools and motels, plazas and fuel stations were built adjacent to residential buildings in interior areas, evident in areas like Kasuwan Dare. This is due to the increasing population and demands of the population. The housing patterns in Gwagwalada as of 2020 had become congested and therefore, slum settlements in areas like Dagiri, Angwan Dodo and Kasuwan Dare had developed.

Housing Policies: In 2012, the government implemented housing policies to address challenges resulting from rapid population growth. These policies aimed to improve livability by promoting the development of affordable housing units and upgrading existing residential areas. The focus was on enhancing housing conditions and ensuring adequate provision of social amenities to meet the needs of the growing population.³⁵ Houses in Gwagwalada during the period between 2007-2020 were relatively less expensive compared to the areas in the city centre in the Abuja Municipal centre such as Garki, Asokoro, Maitama and Wuse, among others. However, the housing policy initiative was not a complete success because as of 2020, the housing conditions in Gwagwalada had deteriorated, with several interviewees such as Mr Samuel Hashim, Mr Samuel Ojo, Khalifa and others, noting that social amenities such as water supply and electricity supply had deteriorated compared to a decade before 2020.

Environmental Management: The government also recognized the environmental implications of unplanned settlements, therefore in 2015, and policies were introduced to manage waste disposal and promote environmental

Scientific & Engineering Research, vol. 9, no. 10, 2018, 2147.

³⁵ Adenyuma, I. Gabriel and Adenyuma O. Mercy. "Assessment of Housing

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Livability in Gwagwalada Town, Abuja, Nigeria." Dutse Journal of Economics and Development Studies 6, no. 2, December 2018, 12.

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sustainability.³⁶ These policies aimed to improve waste management practices and reduce the environmental impact of urbanisation in Gwagwalada. Interviewees claim that this particular initiative, though true, was short lived. Mr Samuel Ojo explained that in 2015, to avoid land pollution with refuse on all corners of the road, the government introduced trucks which went from doorstep to doorstep to collect refuse twice a week.³⁷ He further explained that before the end of 2015, these trucks had reduced their frequency from once a week to once a month and then completely disappeared.

Consequences of Urbanisation in Gwagwalada (2007–2020)

The findings and discussions presented in this paper reveal that the rapid urbanisation of Gwagwalada between 2007 and 2020 was accompanied by several notable challenges. As the population increased and the town expanded spatially, various consequences unfolded across housing, infrastructure, environment and security. The following sub-

sections highlight these key outcomes as observed from the study's discussions.

Pressure on Housing and Expansion of Informal Settlements: The rapid population increase in Gwagwalada created a strong demand for housing which the existing stock could not meet. This resulted in overcrowding, conversion of residential buildings into mixed-use structures, and the growth of informal settlements especially in areas like Dagiri, Old Kutunku and Angwan Dodo. Unregulated structures began spreading into peri-urban zones, reflecting weak development control.

Strain on Social Amenities and Physical Infrastructure: The town's amenities struggled to accommodate the growing population. Water supply, electricity, healthcare, education and transportation facilities faced increased pressure, resulting in shortages and periodic service disruptions.³⁸ Much of this strain stemmed from the mismatch between rapid urban growth and the limited planning and infrastructural investment of the Area Council.

³⁶ Oguche, J. Christopher, Andrew Noah, and Samuel Gwani. "The Implications of Unplanned Settlement on Environmental Quality in Gwagwalada Town." *International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science*, 1, no. 1, 2019, 4.

³⁷ Interview with Samuel, Ojo. c38, welder, Behind FCDA Quarters, 18 Dec. 2024.

³⁸ Sylvester, Anthony. "Sustainability Implications of Residential Development Pattern in Gwagwalada." *International Journal of Environmental Research & Earth Science*, vol. 7, no. 4, Mar. 2025, 35.

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Environmental Stress: Interviews pointed to waste management challenges, blocked drainage channels, which made pollution more common as the built-up area expanded.³⁹ This was further confirmed by the work of Ekpeter, Ekeh and Ezeichi. They noted that inadequate waste management systems were identified to have led to the accumulation of refuse in various parts of the town.⁴⁰ These environmental pressures negatively affected both public health and the natural landscape of the Area Council.

Rising Insecurity: Interview findings pointed to a gradual rise in insecurity ranging from petty theft to more serious crimes, including burglary, armed robbery, motorcycle snatching and kidnapping incidents.⁴¹ Media and police reports highlighted increasing criminal activity in rapidly growing neighbourhoods.⁴² These trends were linked to unemployment, high population density, and socio-economic pressures associated with migration. Residents

frequently expressed concerns about safety, especially in under-policed or poorly lit areas.

Conclusion

This paper examined migration patterns and urbanisation in Gwagwalada between 2007 and 2020, showing how urban drift reshaped the town's demographic and socio-economic landscape. The study found that Gwagwalada's population more than doubled within the period, driven by both urban-to-urban and rural-to-urban migration. The influx resulted in the expansion of unplanned settlements, overstretched infrastructure, and shifts in the town's demographic composition. However, the work also found that these developments also heightened insecurity. The study concludes that Gwagwalada's transformation into a key satellite town among others in the FCT reflects the opportunities and vulnerabilities that accompany rapid urbanisation in Nigeria.

³⁹ Interview with Samuel, Ojo. c38, welder, Behind FCDA Quarters, 18 Dec. 2024.

⁴⁰ Ekpeter, Kenneth, Ekeh Faith and Eziechi Nkechi. "Housing Conditions in the FCT, Abuja-Nigeria: A Case Study of Gwagwalada Satelite Town" *Journal of Environmental Science*, 9, 2019, 100-118.

⁴¹ Interview with Khalifa, Al-adam. c35, Political Elite and Realtor, Town Hall Axis, 16 Dec. 2024.

⁴² Ahmed, Romoke. "Canada Supports Community Policing in Gwagwalada." *Daily Trust*, 20 Jan. 2015, <http://dailytrust.com/canada-supports-community-policing-in-gwagwalada>. Accessed 7 May 2025.

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